

Unorganized Workers in India and Social Security

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Introduction:

In India Unorganized Labour force is higher than the organized labour force. According to government reports, near about 94% of India's workforce is employed in informal or unorganized jobs. This indicates the number of workers who have lack of formal contracts, job security, and social security protection. Although their huge contribution to the economy, they remain excluded the safety net of comprehensive social security systems. These workers are mostly belongs to agricultural laborers and construction workers to domestic helpers and gig economy participants.

Government initiatives like, the **Unorganized Workers' Social Security Act (2008)**, the **Code on Social Security (2020)**, and the **e-Shram portal (2021)** have tried to bring informal workers under social protection. By 2025, more than **310 million workers** registered

on e-Shram, generating a national database for smooth delivery of social welfare.

Objectives:

1. To understand importance and share of unorganized workers in India.
2. To study Social Security coverage for unorganized workers in India.
3. To identify problems faced by unorganized workers in India.

Research Methodology:

Present research is based on quantitative and Qualitative types of data which is collected by primary and secondary sources of data collection. To collect primary data for present research schedule has used and secondary data has collected through available literature related to the topic. 250 samples are selected by random sampling technique form Jalna and Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar.

Discussion:

State wise Information about Registered Unorganized Workers with E-Shram in India:

State/UT	Approx. Workers (in cr)	Share of Total (%)	Main Areas of Work
Uttar Pradesh	8.5	27%	Largest contributor; agriculture & migrant labor dominate.
Bihar	3.5	11%	Heavy rural workforce; seasonal migration to other states.
West Bengal	3.2	10%	Street vending, transport, domestic work.
Madhya Pradesh	2.5	8%	Agriculture and tribal labor significant.

Maharashtra	2.3	7%	Urban informal jobs in Metro Cities, Agriculture, gig economy rising.
Rajasthan	2.1	7%	Mining, construction, handicrafts.
Odisha	1.9	6%	Migrant labor in textiles & construction.
Jharkhand	1.7	5%	Mining and agriculture.
Tamil Nadu	1.6	5%	Textiles, construction, domestic work.
Karnataka	1.5	5%	Gig/platform jobs, services, agriculture.
Kerala	1.2	4%	Migrant inflows; domestic and service work.
Punjab & Haryana	1.5 (combined)	5%	Agriculture and migrant labor.
Delhi (NCT)	0.8	3%	Street vendors, gig workers, construction.
Assam	0.7	~2%	Agriculture, small trade.
Other North-East States	0.6 (combined)	~2%	Agriculture, handicrafts, small trade.
Smaller States/UTs (Goa, Chandigarh, Ladakh, Andaman & Nicobar, etc.)	0.5 (Combined)	~2%	Tourism, services, small-scale trade.

Source: E-Shram Portal, GOI.

An unorganized worker in India refers to workers who are not covered by formal contracts or labor laws, as it performing the pivotal role of employment in the country. This sector contributes around **50% of India's GDP**, identifying its importance to the economy. Workers in informal employment mostly face problems like, irregular incomes, often below minimum wage standards, and lack of benefits such as provident fund, health insurance, or pensions.

The Code on Social Security, 2020:

It is one of India's new four major labor codes, authorized to combine and simplify the country's social security laws. It merges **9 existing legislature** into a single code, including the Employees' Provident Funds Act, Employees State Insurance Act, Maternity Benefit Act, and Building and Other Construction Workers Welfare Cess Act. The motto is to create an **integrated legal framework** that expands social security coverage to all types of workers—

organized unorganized, gig, and platform workers.

The most important characteristic of this code is the **acknowledgement of gig and platform workers for the first time in Indian law**. The Code initiated a **Social Security Fund** to give money for these workers schemes, along with grants from the government, employers, and aggregators. It also has facilities for women, ensuring **180 days of maternity leave, daycare facilities, and work-from-home options**.

The Code extends the coverage of **Employees' Provident Fund (EPFO)** and **Employees' State Insurance Corporation (ESIC)**, covering more facilities and workers under compulsory social security. It also structured national and state-level boards for unorganized workers, building workers, and gig workers to monitor welfare schemes. To upgrade compliance, the Code featured a **technology-based "Inspector-cum-Facilitator" system**, digital record-maintaining, and decriminalization of minor offences, making it easier for businesses to use while ensuring workers' rights.

Data Analysis:

Table No. 1: Education of the respondents

Category/ Education Level	Illiterate	Primary	Secondary	Higher Secondary	Graduation	Post Graduation	Total
SC	8	15	20	9	10	8	70
ST	9	6	7	6	2	0	30
OBC	5	13	12	7	10	3	50
OPEN	10	20	15	22	8	5	80
EWS	2	5	7	2	2	2	20
Total	34	59	61	46	32	18	250

Above Table No. 1, is indication that, most of respondents were found educated upto secondary level followed by primary education. Number of post graduate respondents were found high in SC category and zero in ST category. Overall respondents were found less in graduation and post-graduation level of education.

Table No. 2: Work Nature & Wages of the respondents

Nature of Work	No of Workers	Daily Wages (Rs)
Casual	70	200
Daily Wage	65	250
Contract	25	320
Agriculture	90	150
Total	250	-

Above Table No. 2, is showing data of respondents engaged in different work nature, 90 respondents were found that they were working in agriculture field followed by casual labour and daily wage labour, number of contract workers were found very less as compare to other workers. About wages only contractual workers were getting wages as per government policy otherwise rest of all respondents were found that they were not getting wages as per government policy.

Table No. 3: Problems faced by the respondents

Problems	No of Workers	
	Yes	No
Low & Irregular Wages	230	20
Lack of Basic Facilities at Workplace	145	105
Poor Working Condition	190	60
Lack of Social Security	230	20

Above Table No.3, is informing us about problems faced by the respondents. 230 respondents said that they were facing problem of low, irregular and lack of social security, 190 respondents were found that they were facing problem of poor working condition followed by 145 workers who were facing problem of lack of basic facilities at working place.

Problems Summary:

Unorganized workers in India face a wide range of problems that make their lives insecure and vulnerable. The most pressing issue is the **lack of job security**, as most of them work without formal contracts and can be dismissed at any time without notice or compensation. Their **wages are often irregular and below minimum standards**, leaving them unable to meet basic needs. They also suffer from **poor working conditions**, with little regard for occupational

safety, especially in sectors like construction, mining, and agriculture. Another major challenge is the **absence of social security benefits** such as health insurance, provident funds, pensions, or maternity benefits, which exposes them to financial distress during illness, accidents, or old age.

References:

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